

Causes of Poor Family Nutrition and Sustainable Health of Children in Rural Communities of Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja

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Abstract

Nutrition is a fundamental pillar of human life, health, and development across the entire life span. More than 800 million people in the world still suffer from hunger and over two billion are victims of malnutrition. In Nigeria, there are approximately 1.7 million children suffering from severe acute malnutrition and poor health. It is on this note that this study investigated the causes of poor family nutrition and sustainable health of children in rural communities. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population consisted of 1,040 households in five selected geo-political wards in Gwagwalada Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory. The sample consisted of 210 households that were selected, using purposive sampling technique. Fourteen items structured questionnaire titled "Family Nutrition Questionnaire (FNQ)" was used as the instrument for data collection. Content validity was used. A pilot study was conducted at Kuje community in Abuja. Test-retest method of reliability was used to obtain the internal consistency. The reliability index was obtained through Cronbach's alpha (0.78). Out of 210 questionnaires administered, 197 were valid, representing 94% success rate. Data collected was imputed into the SPSS (25) software package where statistics, in the form of tables were generated. The study discovered that majority of households in rural communities have adequate knowledge of the causes of poor nutritional status of children (64%,54.8%) respectively, and have adequate knowledge of the consequences of poor health status of children (61.4%,60.9%,). It is concluded that there is knowledge of households on the causes of poor nutrition and health status of children. It was recommended that there should be adequate knowledge of low-cost nutritional diets and proper management of available food among households and Home Economics educators should organize town-hall meeting to give orientation to households about family nutrition.

Key words: Family Nutrition, Nutrition, Health, Sustainable Health, Malnutrition

Introduction

Nutrition is a fundamental pillar of human life, health, and development across the entire life span. From the earliest stages of fetal development, at birth and into adulthood and old ages, proper food and good nutrition are essential for survival, physical growth, mental development, performance, and wellbeing (World Health Organization, 2002). According to Ojo (2012), human cells are like microscopic energy making machines and just like machines, needs to be properly maintained

to remain in good working condition, when the human cells do not receive the correct nutritional food, these cells make the body become sluggish and suffer from inadequate nutrition.

Ojo (2012) asserted that nutrition is the study of food in relation to the physiological processes that depend on absorption by the body. Its' functions are for (Growth, energy production, repairs of the body tissue). According to Couillard (2018), more than 800 million people in the world still suffer

from hunger and over two billion are victims of malnutrition. Similarly, Graziano da Silva (2018) revealed that despite considerable progress, almost all countries continue to contend with the multiple burdens of malnutrition: More than 800 million people are undernourished; more than two billion people suffer from micronutrient deficiencies, while in parallel 1.8 billion adults are overweight or obese. In fact, in many countries and households, these various burdens of malnutrition coexist, hinting at just how complex the issue of malnutrition really is.

In respect to the nutritional status of households, the Education for All (EFA) Global Monitoring Report as cited by UNESCO (2011) states that more than a quarter of children below fifteen years of age in sub-Saharan Africa are underweight due to poor diet and malnutrition, making them more vulnerable to disease and less able to concentrate at school (UNESCO, 2011). In Nigeria, in term of nutritional status of the households, the UNICEF (2015) asserted that approximately 1.7 million children suffer from severe acute malnutrition. This number constitutes one tenth of all severely acutely malnourished children in the world (UNICEF, 2015). According to the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (2014), Nigeria has the second highest acute malnutrition burden in the world, with an estimated 3.78 million children suffering from malnutrition. These revelations implied that many Nigeria families lack required nutrients that can improve nutritional health.

ShapeFit (2020) describes family nutrition as encouraging healthy eating attitudes and behaviors within the family unit. Every family has nutrition habits. The concern is whether these habits are healthy or unhealthy. Since every family member is unique and has different nutritional needs, everyone's needs should be considered in the family nutrition plan. There are a number of nutrients that individuals; particularly the children need to ensure proper development and sustainable health. According to Shediak-Rizkallah and Bone (1998), sustainable health means "the maintenance of health benefits over time." Sustainable

health is a personal commitment to maintaining and taking responsibility for one's own health, through preventative (proactive) means. This means not only having regular exercise, and taking care of what one eats, but also maintaining a healthy and balanced state of mind.

According to UNICEF (2006), children in Nigeria are falling short of meeting some of their daily nutritional requirements which can improve and sustain health. Generally, it is the management and optimization of nutrients that amounts to a healthy diet. In fact, there are no bad food, only badly managed diets (Ojo, 2012). The British Nutrition Foundation (2005) did a summary of nutrients traditionally considered important in certain amounts for a healthy status of families to include zinc, iron, carbohydrates, vitamins, essential fatty acids, and minerals.

In many families, the major food that is consumed is carbohydrate, which is food rich in starch such as *asgarri*, *elubo*, *eba*, *fufu*, yam, cocoyam and pap. This frequent consumption of carbohydrate rich food also has direct negative influence on health status of children. Several factors have been identified to have affected family nutrition and sustainable health of children in the family - Poverty, diseases, family size, household income and expenditure, household food security and insecurity (Chaudhury, Akhter, Haque, Aziz, & Nahar, 2009; Oquntin, 2010; Etim, 2016; Kalu and Etim, 2018). Climate change is one of the critical concerns for food security (Graziano da Silva, 2018). Climate change represents a substantial, transversal, and complex additional challenge to critical situation, and without urgent action, people will be at risk of hunger and malnutrition (Graziano da Silva, 2018). Climate change, also called global warming, refers to the rise in average surface temperatures on Earth. An overwhelming scientific consensus maintains that climate change is due primarily to the human use of fossil fuels, which releases carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases into the air. The gases trap heat within the atmosphere, which can have a range of effects on ecosystems, including rising sea levels, severe weather events, and

droughts that render landscapes more susceptible to wildfires.

Graziano da Silva (2018) reveals that climate change already affects all four dimension of food security: availability of food; physical and economic access to food; utilization of food in terms of how it is used and assimilated by the human body; and stability of these three dimensions. Climate change affects agriculture and food production around the world because of high temperatures, elevated CO₂ level, extreme events, modified pests and weeds, and modified transpiration and precipitation regimes (FAO, 2008). Low latitude regions coupled with the above factors increase the risk of decreased crop yields. In contrast, high latitude areas are likely to experience crop yield increases. Nigeria is one of the countries seriously affected by climate changes leading to recurrent flood, partly due to deforestation and poor land management practices. Nigeria has suffered decreased crop and animals yields due to climate change and other avoidable crisis such as herdsmen and Famers conflicts (Metu, Okeyika, &Maduka, 2016). These problems are evident across the country leading to increased food shortages among household. This has contributed to poor family nutrition, unacceptable dietary practices, and poor health status of many households in many rural communities especially in Gwagwalada Area Council, Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. This study sought to find out the knowledge households have on the causes of malnutrition to propose household solutions to these challenges

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to identify the causes of poor family nutrition and sustainable health of children in rural communities of Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja. The specific objectives of the investigation were to:

1. Ascertain the knowledge level of households on the causes of poor nutritional status of children in rural communities of Gwagwalada Area Council

2. Determine the knowledge level of households on the consequences of poor health status of children in rural communities of Gwagwalada Area Council
3. Identify solutions to the problems of poor family nutrition among children in rural communities of Gwagwalada Area Council.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The descriptive research design is used in social science research to gather information from people on their perceptions, opinions, and beliefs over a critical concern. The findings of a survey descriptive design are generalizable.

Population for the Study

The population consisted of one thousand and forty (1,040) households in five geo-political wards that were purposively selected out of all the ten geo-political wards in Gwagwalada Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The wards were Zuba, DobiKutunku, Tunga Maje, and Ikwa. These wards were included in the study because they were majorly rural communities.

Sample for the Study

The sample consisted of two hundred and ten (210) households that were selected, using purposive sampling technique. 42 households from each of the five (5) purposively selected communities formed the respondents.

Method of Data Collection

Fourteen items self-structured questionnaire titled "Family Nutrition Questionnaire (FNQ)" was used as the instrument for data collection. The questionnaire elicited "high extent" and "low extent" responses. The instrument was validated for content. A pilot study was conducted at Kuje community in Abuja. A total of 20 copies of the questionnaire were administered to selected households. Test-retest method of reliability was used to obtain the internal consistency. The reliability index was

obtained through Cornbrash's alpha (0.78). Translating to the suitability of the instrument to elicit the correct responses.

The questionnaire was administered by the researchers with the help of four research assistants. The researchers, with the four research assistants gathered the respondents on community basis in the town hall meeting. It took the researchers three (3) weeks to complete the exercise. Out of 210 questionnaires administered, 197 were valid, representing 94% success rate.

Data Analysis Techniques

The analyses of data collected were carried out based on the objectives of the study. Data collected were imputed into the SPSS (25) software package. The results are presented in tables. The simple percentage was used to determine the level of awareness. The benchmark for determining the high level of awareness was set at 50% and above, while the level of awareness below 50% was deemed low level of awareness.

Results

The results of the knowledge level of households on the causes of poor nutritional status of children as presented on Table 1 reveals that the sampled households (61.4%) were aware of climate change as the cause of poor nutrition, against (38.6%) that were not aware. Large numbers of the households (54.8%) were aware that decreased crop and animal yields result in poor nutrition of children against 45.2% that were not aware. Majority of the household were aware that poverty affect the quality of food that household eats (64%) as against 36% that were not aware. Majority of the households (58.4%) were aware that large family size negatively affects family nutrition as against 41.6% that were not aware. Large numbers of the households (60.4%) were aware that household food insecurity contributes to under-nutrition as against 39.6% that were not aware. The study shows that majority of households in rural communities have adequate knowledge of the causes of poor nutritional status of children.

Table 1: Knowledge Level of Households on The Causes of Poor Nutritional Status of Children

S/N	Items	N	High Extent	Percent	Low Extent	Percent	Total Percent
1.	Extent to which one is aware of climate change as the cause of poor nutrition in your household	197	121	61.4	76	38.6	100.0
2.	The extent to which you are aware that decreased crop and animal yields result in poor nutrition of children	197	108	54.8	89	45.2	100.0
3.	What extents are you aware that poverty affect the quality of food that household eats?	197	126	64.0	71	36.0	100.0
4.	Extent to which one is aware that large family size negatively affects family nutrition	197	115	58.4	82	41.6	100.0
5.	The extent you are aware that household food insecurity contributes to under-nutrition	197	119	60.4	78	39.6	100.0

The results of the knowledge level of households on the consequences of poor health status of children as presented in Table 2 reveals that the sampled households (58.4%) were aware that poor health result in stunted growth in children as against (41.6%) that were not aware. Large numbers of the households (57.9%) were

aware that sickness makes children less able to concentrate at school as against 42.1% that were not aware. Majority of the household (60.9%) were aware that poor health makes children to become underweight as against 39.1% that were not aware. Majority of the households (61.4%) were aware that poor family health drains

the family finances as against 38.6% that were not aware. The study shows that majority of households in rural communities

have adequate knowledge of the consequences of poor health status of children.

Table 2: Knowledge Level of Households on The Consequences of Poor Health Status Of Children

S/N	Variables	*N	High Extent	Percent	Low Extent	Percent	Total Percent
1.	Extent to which you are aware that poor health result in stunted growth in children	197	115	58.4	82	41.6	100.0
2.	Extent to which you are aware that sickness makes children less able to concentrate at school	197	114	57.9	83	42.1	100.0
3.	What extent are you aware that poor health makes children to become underweight?	197	120	60.9	77	39.1	100.0
4.	Extent to which you are aware that poor family health drains the family finances	197	121	61.4	76	38.6	100.0

The results of solutions to the problems of poor family nutrition among children as presented in Table 3 shows that majority of the households (32%) were of the view that aggressive citizens' climate change awareness campaign is a better strategy for increasing the knowledge level of households. 20.8% of the households favored adequate knowledge of low-cost nutritional diets and proper management of

available food. 18.2% of the households believed increased financial supports for research is a better strategy. While 16.2% favored improvement of the quality of primary health care system, 12.7% were of the view that provision of physical and social amenities by government will go a long way in solving the problems of poor family nutrition among children.

Table 3: Solutions to The Problems of Poor Family Nutrition Among Children

S/n	Variables	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1.	Aggressive citizens' climate change awareness campaign	63	32.0	32.0
2.	Adequate knowledge of low-cost nutritional diets and proper management of available food	41	20.8	52.8
3.	Increased financial supports for research	36	18.3	71.1
4.	Improvement of the quality of primary health care system	32	16.2	87.3
5.	Provision physical and social amenities by government	25	12.7	100.0
	Total	197	100.0	

Discussion

The results in Table 1 shows that majority of households in rural communities have adequate knowledge of the causes of poor nutritional status of children. These findings were in line with the study by Graziano da Silva (2018) who reveals that climate change which is one of the major causes of food insecurity already affects all four dimension of food security: availability of food; physical and economic access to food; utilization of

food in terms of how it is used and assimilated by the human body; and stability of these three dimensions. These problems are evident across the country leading to increased food shortages among household. The fact that in many households, the major food that is consume is carbohydrate, which is food rich in starch such as *asgarri, elubo, eba, fufu, yam, cocoyam* and pap does not make many families to understand that climate

change has significant influence on the quality of food consumed.

The findings in Table 2 reveals that majority of households in rural communities have adequate knowledge of the consequences of poor health status of children. The findings were in line with UNESCO(2011) that more than a quarter of children below fifteen years of age in sub-Saharan Africa are underweight due to poor diet and malnutrition, making them more vulnerable to disease and less able to concentrate at school. In Nigeria, in term of nutritional status of the households, the UNICEF (2015) asserted that approximately 1.7 million children suffer from severe acute malnutrition. The consumption of low-quality agricultural produce has significant negative effects on human health, causing sicknesses and in extreme case, death due to food poisoning.

The findings in Table 3 shows that majority of the households were of the view that aggressive citizens' climate change awareness campaign is a better solution for increasing the knowledge level of households on the causes of poor family nutrition and sustainable health of children. The households also favored adequate knowledge of low-cost nutritional diets and proper management of available food. This finding agreed with Ojo (2012) that it is the management and optimization of nutrients that amounts to a healthy diet. In fact, there are no bad food, only badly managed diets. It also agreed with Graziano da Silva (2018) that a better understanding of the pathways linking climate change and nutrition is critical for developing interventions that ensures that the world's population has access to not only sufficient, but also safe and nutritious food.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The knowledge level of households on the causes of poor nutrition and health status of children is high. But many children are still faced with several food-related concerns, such as poor nutrition and hunger. Proper family nutrition is critical to maximizing brain function of children. Access of families to nutrition that

incorporates protein, carbohydrates, and glucose has been shown to improve children's cognition, concentration, and energy levels. Nutritional deficiencies early in life particularly zinc, vitamins, fatty acids, and protein can affect the cognitive development of school-aged children. From the results of this study, it is therefore recommended that:

1. Government at all levels through relevant ministries, parastatals, agencies, and non-governmental organizations should sensitize the households in rural communities on adequate knowledge of low-cost nutritional diets and proper management of available food. Furthermore, The Federal government should increase financial supports for research on improved agricultural seeds and high breed farm animal that could withstand any climate change.
2. Private donors and philanthropists should improve the quality of primary health care system in the country. This is to enable the less privileged individuals to get qualitative health advice from health practitioners.
3. Every household should learn about low-cost nutritional diets and proper management of available food to improve health. Every household should have small vegetable garden in their compound. This could help to supplement the excessive consumption of carbohydrate food.
4. Home economics educators should organize town-hall meeting to give orientation to households about the causes, consequences, and solution to the problems of poor family nutrition.

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